

Indian Television Rating Point Policy 2026: an overview

Amit Sharma, Ph.D.

Assistant Professor, Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, University of Allahabad, Bharat.

Email: jmcamit@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9589-2245>

Vimal Mohan, Ph.D.

Senior Sports Editor, NDTV India

Email: vimal236@gmail.com

Abstract

Television Rating Points (TRPs) are, in a way, a driving force for the Indian television industry. They indicate channels' popularity, a program's success, and advertising revenue. In India's multi-channel culture, competition among channels often leads to a tendency to choose the easier path of sensationalism over infotainment. India has also witnessed declining content quality and manipulation among TV channels. Hence, questions about TRP credibility and transparency have become prevalent.

This study analyses the evolution of India's TRP policy from its inception to the Television Rating Policy 2026. Television in India began in 1959 and expanded with colour broadcasting in 1982. Until the 1990s, *Doordarshan* held a monopoly and TRP was not an issue. Post-1991 liberalization introduced a culture and business of private channels. This intensified competition, and TRP became the primary metric for advertising. TAM Media Research pioneered audience measurement in the 1990s. But concerns over the reliability of research-based measurement led to the Government of India's 2014 TRP guidelines. Under these guidelines, BARC was appointed as the official body. The guidelines mandated data confidentiality and household panel rotation to ensure fairness. However, over time, shifts in viewers' habits toward mobile and OTT platforms, along with TRP-related controversies, made reforms necessary. The TV Rating Point Policy 2026 addresses these challenges. It has:

- A) reduced the net worth requirement for rating agencies,
- B) mandated board independence,
- C) expanded the sample size to 120,000 homes, and
- D) integrated data from DTH, cable, internet, and connected TV.
- E) It has also introduced mandatory quarterly internal audits and annual third-party audits to enhance transparency.

The 2026 policy is an attempt to modernize measurement by emphasizing technology. It aims to restore credibility. While global systems such as Nielsen, BARB, and OzTAM already include cross-platform measurement, India's earlier focus was TV-centric. Now, the 2026 policy aims to make TRP a more accurate, transparent reflection of India's evolving media consumption.

Keywords: *TV audience measurement, popularity of program, OTT, digital media, news, new TV policy*

Introduction

TRP stands for Television Rating Point. It is a certified measure to gauge the popularity and audience numbers of specific TV programs or channels in the field of news and entertainment, used in over 100 countries worldwide. Higher TRP is considered evidence that a larger number of people have watched a particular program during a specific time period. The importance of a Television Rating Point, or TRP, has always been very high in the TV industry. The popularity of any channel, the success of its programs, and the rate of advertisements all depend on TRP. The rise or fall in the TRP of any program reflects its popularity among people. Higher TRP means that more and more viewers watch that program, and that program is receiving more advertisements and revenue. However, in the era of commercialization, television channels have adopted new tactics for cheap popularity to increase TRP. Instead of clean infotainment, news or entertainment, the work of selling vulgarity to the audience has been done, and news channels have started selling drama instead of news (Nayak, 2021). In some cases, news channels have affected the television rating research. In such a scenario, the Government of India replaced the old TRP policy of 2014 with the TV Rating Policy 2026. The present article attempts to analyze the TRP policy from its initial to the current form.

The television started in India in 1959. In 1982, television became coloured and live broadcasting also became possible. After this, the popularity of television increased greatly. In the 1980s, TV serials like *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata* were so popular that streets would empty during their broadcast. People finished essential work early and sat in front of their TV sets ahead of time. Beyond families, entire villages and communities gathered together, turning television into a platform for community viewing. Even after this, several popular programs like *Hum Log*, *Buniyaad*, and *Chitrahaar* increased the popularity of TV in Indian society. However, by then, *Doordarshan* had a monopoly in India. Since there were no private channels, there was no competition among channels. Channels like *Doordarshan's* DD Metro were operating (Jalarajan & Suresh, 2023). Until the mid-1990s, TRP was not an issue in India. After the economic crisis in 1991, the LPG (Liberalization, Privatization, and Globalization) policy adopted by the Government of India had a profound impact on Indian news channels and the television industry (Ahmad, 2021). This policy ended the government monopoly in the news and entertainment sector and opened the doors for private sector television channels (Belladi, 2025).

The beginning of audience measurement in the 1990s was through TAM Media Research. TAM Media Research played an important role in the field of television audience measurement (TRP) in India, which introduced modern techniques in media measurement. The expansion and standardization of cable and satellite TV in India began in the early 1990s. It completely transformed the landscape of Indian television. TRP became the main source for advertising, and channels started chasing programs that increased ratings and sensational journalism. As a result, competition in the media increased rapidly, and the importance of the TRP system to understand viewers' preferences grew even more. Amid this growing need, there was a demand to regulate the TRP system. Initially, agencies like TAM measured viewer preferences, but continuous questions were raised about the transparency and reliability of these agencies. Keeping this in mind, in 2014 the government issued guidelines for the TRP system for the first time, so that audience research could have a robust framework and people could continue to trust TRP. Issuing new guidelines for TRP was a major structural change. Under this policy, the Broadcast Audience Research Council (BARC) was officially given the responsibility of measuring TRP in India. The main objective of the 2014 policy was to make the system transparent and fair. It ensured that no channel or advertiser could influence the agency involved in measuring TRP (Kulkarni, 2024).

The TRP policy issued in 2014 made it mandatory to change 25 percent of the households included in the panel every year to maintain the accuracy and confidentiality of the data. This rotation was to be carried out in a phased manner each month so that new households could replace the old ones. These guidelines were much better for tracking cable TV and satellite. At that time, this step was quite necessary because the TRP system got a strong framework (Kulkarni, 2024). But over time, new challenges started to emerge. Audience habits began to change. People started watching TV content not only on television but also on mobile and OTT platforms. In addition, controversies related to TRP also affected the credibility of the system (S. Kumar et al., 2021).

TV rating policy 2026

Now, if we talk about 2026, the TRP system is not the same as before. Today, it cannot be limited to just TV. Therefore, work is now being done to include digital viewership in it. Emphasis is being given on increasing sample size, making data collection more scientific, and conducting technology-based research. At the same time, monitoring of the system has also

become stricter than before to prevent any kind of irregularity. On March 27, 2026, the new TV rating policy 2026 was implemented. The main objective of this policy is to improve the measurement of TRP and to bring accurate audience figures to light (Dutta, 2026).

Several important changes have been made under the new policy. Firstly, the net worth requirement for rating agencies has been reduced from 20 crore to 5 crore, making it easier for new agencies to enter this sector. Additionally, it has been made mandatory that at least 50% of the board of directors should have no association with any broadcaster, advertiser, or advertising agency. This will help prevent conflicts of interest and maintain the impartiality of the system. At the same time, agencies have also been prohibited from providing consultancy services that could affect impartiality (Bansal, 2026).

The new policy also emphasizes increasing the sample size. The new policy clarifies that agencies will have to expand their operations to 80,000 surveyed homes within 18 months. However, the same work has to be done in 6 months for the existing rating agency. Research agencies will eventually have to reach 120,000 homes to improve the accuracy of the data (Bansal, 2026). A major change has also been made at the technological level. Now, data collection will be promoted through DTH, cable, internet, and connected TV, which will help in better understanding the actual preferences of the audience. Along with this, the dual audit system has been made mandatory. Internal audits will have to be conducted every quarter, and the Ministry of Information and Broadcasting of India will have to be provided with complete information in this regard. In this context, once a year, the entire research data will have to be externally audited by a chartered accountant (CA) or firm. This will strengthen transparency and accountability in the system.

Television Rating Points and manipulation

Television Rating Points (TRP) is primarily indicators of popularity of Indian television shows or programs. They are a market driver for stories and TV shows. The TRP is very important because advertising revenue worth thousands of crores depends on it. However, the TRP is also faces manipulation and scandals. Hence policy reforms become the need of the hours. Some of the most notable recent controversies are as follows:

The 2020 TRP Scam: The 2020 TRP scam, or TRP controversy, shook the entire television industry in India. It led to the TRP Policy 2026 reforms. In October 2020, Mumbai Police and

the Broadcast Audience Research Council (BARC) alleged that several TV channels manipulated TRPs by bribing households. During this time, serious allegations were also made that houses equipped with BARC's 'BAR-o-meter' were paid monthly to manipulate TRP. These homes received cash to keep specific channels running continuously, without the audience. This artificially inflated viewership numbers, which were then reflected in TRP charts. The channels involved in the controversy included Republic TV, Box Cinema, and *Fakt Marathi*, among others. Arnab Goswami's channel 'Republic TV' was the primary accused. Mumbai Police claimed that Republic TV manipulated data to become the No. 1 English news channel (Saigal, 2020). Republic denied charges and called this action a "witch-hunt." Two other channels were also named in the FIR for paying households ₹400–₹500 per month to watch them. 'News Nation' and 'India Today' were also initially named, but they were later given a clean chit.

Major actions were taken to prevent manipulation: **A)** BARC suspended weekly ratings for all news channels for 12 weeks, from October 2020 to January 2021 (Press Trust of India, 2020), to review its system. **B)** The Ministry of Information and Broadcasting (I&B) formed a committee under Prasar Bharati CEO Shashi Shekhar Vempati to review TRP guidelines (Jha, 2020). **C)** The case exposed flaws in the 2014 policy, such as: a) a small sample size of only 44,000 metered homes, b) a lack of third-party audits, and c) vulnerability to panel infiltration (Press Trust of India, 2020).

It directly influenced the TRP Policy 2026, which introduced a larger sample size, stricter audits, and reduced entry barriers for new rating agencies.

News Channels and Unhealthy, Sensational Content for TRP: TRP pressure has pushed news channels toward sensationalism. For instance:

A) Sushant Singh Rajput Case Coverage, 2020: Several channels ran 24x7 speculative coverage, conspiracy theories, and live "re-enactments." Republic TV, Times Now, and *Aaj Tak* saw massive TRP spikes during June–August 2020. The News Broadcasting Standards Authority (NBSA) fined channels; called the coverage "highly inappropriate." Critics argued that channels manufactured drama instead of news to chase TRPs (Priyadarshini, 2021).

B) COVID-19 Misinformation: During 2020–21, some channels ran unverified “cures” and pushed communal angles to boost engagement. BARC data showed the news genre’s share jumped from 7% to 21% in March 2020, creating a race for eyeballs.

C) “Media Trials”: Cases like Aarushi Talwar, Sheena Bora, and Hathras were turned into daily soaps. In 2021, the Supreme Court noted that “media trials affect the administration of justice” and are often TRP-driven.

Entertainment channels: Not just news channels, general entertainment channels have also used questionable methods to boost their TRPs. These channels created fake social media chatter and bought YouTube views to generate buzz. There were controversies around BARC’s own functioning too. These included delays in releasing data & an alleged ‘lack of transparency,’ among other issues. Reports indicated that BARC’s 44,000 metered homes under-represented rural India and digital viewers. A channel could trend in cities but have zero rural sample. Hence, the data representing national TRPs was distorted.

Manipulation on OTT Platforms: India has a massive consumer base on OTT platforms, with roughly 45 crore-plus users. The conventional TRP mechanism does not count OTT audiences. Many advertisers have now started focusing on ‘cross-platform measurement’ instead of relying only on BARC.

The 2020 TRP scam was a wake-up call to establish a proper system for India’s multi-channel — 900-plus channel — culture. However, BARC still remains the official method for measuring the popularity metrics of TV channels. The above-mentioned controversies proved that without transparency, technology, and cross-platform measurement, the TRP race can ruin the ecosystem. The TRP Policy 2026 is an attempt to fix these lacunae.

Methodology beyond the Television Rating Point

In India, the work of measuring TRP is mainly carried out by BARC (Broadcast Audience Research Council), which includes organizations like IBDF, ISA, and AAI. Earlier, TAM (AC Nielsen and Kantar) has also worked in this field. BARC was formed in 2014 for TV ratings in India. After joining TAM, BARC has been established as the world's largest TRP measurement agency; it is the country's only rating body that operates for the ratings of television in both the private and government sectors. However, DART, that is, *Doordarshan*

Audience Research TV Ratings, is a government agency that uses only *Doordarshan* viewers as samples for research. DART also include samples from rural areas (Goyal, 2020).

BARC has installed Bar-O-Meters in nearly 6,000 homes with the cooperation of the television audience meter. Bar-O-Meters record programs watched at home on television through special watermarks present in the programs. The use of watermarking technology has brought significant accuracy to BARC's TV rating-related data. Currently, BARC is providing TRP-related services to more than 470 channels. The monitoring team for TV rating research gathers information about programs watched on TV every minute through the Bar-O-Meters. After this, by analyzing these data, the research team releases all the TRP-related figures for all channels (Chaturvedi, 2020).

In today's time, where OTT & digital media platforms are rapidly advancing, the new TRP policy can also prove helpful in understanding the changing preferences of the audience. This will make it soothing for advertisers to reach the right audience. They can plan the best mode and medium for their advertisements more effectively.

Its impact could be visible on the content too. When channels receive accurate and clear data, they will try to create programs according to audience preferences. This will give viewers a better experience. The biggest update in the new TRP-2026 policy has developed according to the audit system. Now, there will be strict monitoring of the rating agencies' work. Periodic third-party audits are mandatory now; strict action has to be taken if any irregularities are detected. The government believes bring transparency into the TRP data and establishing people's trust in the TRP system.

In addition, importance has also been given to increasing the sample size. More households have to include in the process of measuring TRP compared to before. Especially small towns and rural areas have also given a place, allowing the real preferences of the audience to be better reflected. Until now, due to limited samples, questions often arose about whether TRP accurately represents the entire country.

Another significant change in the updated policy is that competition in the field of TRP measurement has to be promoted. Until now, this responsibility mainly rested with the Broadcast Audience Research Council (BARC), but under the new system, other agencies may also get a chance. The main reason behind this decision is to reduce monopoly and increase the reliability of the data.

Traditional TV verses OTT platforms

When traditional TV mediums like DTH (Direct-to-Home) & streaming services are compared, it clearly shows how viewers' preferences are changing. Earlier, people used to watch TV at a scheduled time to see their favorite programs. But now, OTT platforms have drastically changed this entire system. 'On-demand content' provided viewers an opportunity to watch the content of their choice anytime as well as anywhere. During the early days, TV was watched on community TV sets, but with the technology, the TV-watching habit also changed, and TV went to the living room. With the TV, social & cultural changes keeping pace with technology turned TV into a personal medium of entertainment. Now TV can be watched on mobile, iPad, and tablet. All infotainment content for TV is now available on OTT platforms.

DTH is a traditional broadcasting service where content reaches the audience through a specific span and channel. The audience doesn't have the right to change or control this time and channel. In contrast, OTT platforms provide content via the internet, where users can watch movies, web series, or any show as per their convenience. Due to this facility, especially the youth are rapidly being attracted towards OTT. The variety of content on OTT platforms is also more visible. Here, content ranging from regional languages to the international scenario is easily available, whereas in DTH, content is limited to channels. OTT platforms use algorithms to understand audience preferences and suggest content that make audience's experience more personalized (Sharma & Kumar, 2024).

However, DTH service is not completely out of use; it has a very important viewership portion. Especially in rural areas and places where internet access is limited, DTH still remains a reliable medium. People still rely more on DTH for live news, sports, and other real-time programs. The live content of OTT platforms is gradually increasing, but it has not become an alternative to DTH completely. The TRP-2026 policy has been developed with a focus on including digital viewership. Because if data is prepared based on TV viewers only, it will be incomplete. Today's audiences are not limited to TV alone but also watch content on mobile, laptops etc. This shift among the DTH & OTT is not just about technology; it also includes the alteration in the mindset and audience's habits. The aim of the TRP-2026 policy is to create a framework keeping these changes in mind, in which a person can include both traditional and digital mediums.

Television Rating Policy-2026 is a reflection of the changes that happened in the Indian media industry—where transparency and technological development are placed in the middle. If we

compare both TRP policies of 2014 & 2026, the difference can be measured. In 2014, the focus was entirely on establishing and controlling the system, whereas in 2026's policy, the focus is on modernization and making it more reliable. The TRP 2014 guidelines were primarily related to traditional TV, while the 2026 system also takes digital and OTT platforms into account. The TRP policy-2014 laid the foundation, whereas the policy for 2026 is going to strengthen and update that foundation as per the current need. Today, TRP is linked with the credibility of the media industry and audience's trust. So transparency, technology, and reliability is become important in new updated guidelines (Behera, 2026).

Television Rating Point Measurement in World

Television Rating Point (TRP) has always held great importance for the TV industry. The popularity programs, the position of any channel, & advertisement rates largely depend on TRP. In foreign countries, the TRP system measurement is more developed, technically strong, and continuously evolving over the ages. TRP is known as "Audience Measurement" worldwide. Here, it is being measured what people are watching on the TV and what kind of content they are consuming on mobile, laptop, or OTT platforms (Kumar & Sharma, 2023). So, data become more comprehensive and accurate.

Nielsen Company measures TV ratings in America. This company has been working from TRP for years ago and is considered quite reliable. Nielsen's method is both simple and scientific. Under this, some selected households are chosen as samples. In these homes, a special device called a 'People Meter' is installed, which records which channel is being watched more. Every member of the household has a separate identity. With this unique identity, it can be measured which age and class's people is watching the said program. Nowadays, Nielsen has updated its system to include digital platforms.

In Britain, the Broadcasters' Audience Research Board (BARB) conducts TRP measurement. The system here is also quite organized. BARB prepares a group of thousands of households, in which special meters are installed. Whenever a person watches TV, s/he registers her/his presence using a remote. This provides information about which person is watching which program. In this way, very accurate data is collected. Now BARB has also changed the system, and digital platforms like OTT and video streaming services are included in the TRP. It makes it easy to understand the audience's real preferences.

In Australia, OzTAM does the TRP measurement. The OzTAM also uses almost the same method, which relies on sample homes and modern meter technology. In this rating, instead of being limited to traditional TV, digital viewing is also being given importance. Now more effort is being made to know where and how the audience is watching content, not just what they are watching on TV. In China, CSM Media Research performs TRP-rated work. China's network is vast. Here, the TRP agency collects data from a large-scale set-top box along with people meters.

If we look at the TRP policy and process of the major countries in the world as a whole, we will find that there has been a significant change in the measurement and importance of TRP. The measurement of TRP is no longer limited to TV but has now evolved with a 'cross-platform system.' This includes TV, mobile, laptop, & OTT. This makes the data more transparent and reliable. When we compare the TRP measurement policy and process between the India and developing and developed countries, this variance is clearly visible. India's focus is still mainly on TV viewership, whereas in global TRP guidelines, they are a step further to include digital platforms as well. Hence, the collected TRP data is more comprehensive and realistic. The TRP measurement system abroad has developed significantly over time. It has become an important means of measuring the changing habits of audiences and the evolving character of media. India has shifted to an era where TRP is not limited to TV alone; it includes every screen where viewers are watching content.

Conclusion

Keeping the digital era in mind, the new TV Rating Policy-2026 considered the future needs. Today, viewers are, inter alia, traditional TV, and people watching content on mobile and OTT platforms. The new TRP policy is able to cope with the future requirement and bring these platforms within the scope of measurement. Experts believe that the biggest impact of this policy will be on TV channels and the advertising market. Now, channels are focused on the quality of content rather than just increasing TRP. Meanwhile, advertisers will get more reliable data, allowing them to invest in the right platform. Overall, TV Rating Policy-2026 has brought an important change in the Indian media industry. However, its real success will depend on its effective implementation. This policy will provide new strength to transparency and trust. In the beginning, some challenges may arise, such as adopting new technologies and implementing the rules correctly. But gradually, these difficulties can decrease. Overall, the TV Rating Policy 2026 is considered a big and positive step for the Indian media industry.

In this changing era, advertisers had changed their strategy. Earlier, the advertiser used to allot advertisements mainly to TV channels; now they provide an important portion of their advertisements to the OTT and digital platforms. Hence, there was an urgent need to make the TRP system modern and comprehensive so that it could correctly understand the real behaviour of the audience. The new TRP policy is as per the need of the requirement of the time.

References

- Ahmad, W. (2021). Impact of Liberalization Privatization Globalization (LPG) On the Indian Economy: From 1991 To 2019. *Eurasian Journal of Management & Social Sciences*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.23918/ejmss.V2i2p43>
- Bansal, S. (2026, April 3). *New TV Rating Policy Too Little, Too Late?* <https://www.hindustantimes.com/cities/mumbai-news/new-tv-rating-policy-too-little-too-late-101775158868057.html>
- Behera, R. (2026, March 28). *What the new Television Rating Policy means, and why it was needed.* Tribune. <https://www.tribuneindia.com/news/india/what-the-new-television-rating-policy-means-and-why-it-was-needed/>
- Belladi, S. (2025). Transformation of Journalism in India and the rise of the Fifth Estate, a critical appraisal. *Cogent Arts & Humanities*, 12(1), 2498187. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2025.2498187>
- Chaturvedi, M. (2020, October 9). *What is TRP and how it is calculated: Check here.* India Today. <https://www.indiatoday.in/information/story/what-is-trp-and-how-it-is-calculated-check-here-1729909-2020-10-09>
- Dutta, A. N. (2026, March 28). *Govt's new TV Ratings Policy Defines Rules for Accountability, Transparency.* Indian Express. <https://indianexpress.com/article/india/govts-new-tv-ratings-policy-defines-rules-for-accountability-transparency-10605374/>

- Goyal, S. (2020, October 8). *What is TRP and how is it calculated?* Jagranjosh.
<https://www.jagranjosh.com/general-knowledge/what-is-trp-and-how-is-it-calculated-1524137013-1>
- Jalarajan, R. S., & Suresh, A. K. (2023). Indian Television and the Rise of the Local. In S. M. S. Reza & R. K. Roy, *Television Publics in South Asia* (1st ed., pp. 74–90). Routledge India. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003377740-6>
- Jha, L. (2020, November 4). *I&B ministry sets up committee to review guidelines for TV rating agencies*. Mint. <https://www.livemint.com/industry/media/i-b-ministry-sets-up-committee-to-review-guidelines-for-tv-rating-agencies-11604503705796.html>
- Kulkarni, S. (2024, December 10). *What is the Meaning of TRP & How it is calculated?* The Media Ant. <https://www.themediaant.com/blog/what-is-the-meaning-of-trp/>
- Kumar, M., & Sharma, A. (2023). Disinformation and social media: Review of the film *Afwaah*. *Media Asia*, 51(3), 519–524.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/01296612.2023.2244747>
- Kumar, S., Sharma, A., & Verma, V. (2021). Social Media A Tool for Social and Political Inclusion among Youth: A Study of Indian University Students. *Current Research Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4(1), 82–89.
<https://doi.org/10.12944/CRJSSH.4.1.08>
- Nayak, S. N. (2021). New Perspectives on the Annals of R.K. Narayan: Reflections and Ruminations. In L. C. Mihăeș, R. Andreescu, & A. Dimitriu (Eds.), *Advances in Linguistics and Communication Studies* (pp. 300–313). IGI Global.
<https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-7998-6605-3.ch016>
- Press Trust of India. (2020, October 15). *TRP scam: BARC temporarily suspends weekly ratings of news channels*. Times of India. <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/trp->

scam-barc-temporarily-suspends-weekly-ratings-of-news-channels/articleshow/78676994.cms

Priyadarshini, A. (2021, April 16). *NBSA dismisses Aaj Tak's review plea: Will channel now apologise for its Sushant Singh Rajput coverage?* NewsLaundry.

<https://www.newsLaundry.com/2021/04/16/nbsa-dismisses-aaj-taks-review-plea-will-channel-now-apologise-for-its-sushant-singh-rajput-coverage>

Saigal, S. (2020, November 24). *Mumbai police file charge sheet in TRP manipulation case.*

The Hindu. <https://www.thehindu.com/news/cities/mumbai/mumbai-police-file-charge-sheet-in-trp-manipulation-case/article33167256.ece>

Sharma, A., & Kumar, M. (2024). Infodemic, migration and social inequality: Review of the film *Bheed*. *Media Asia*, 51(3), 512–518.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/01296612.2023.2210433>